

what **exactly** is bioinformatics?

Dr Georgie Samaha

Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney

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Hello

- Bioinformatics group lead at Sydney Informatics Hub.
- Building digital public infrastructure with the Australian BioCommons.
- PhD in mammalian genetics and genomics.
- Learned bioinformatics out of necessity.
- Made many mistakes along the way.

My confidence in my ability to 'do' bioinformatics

Today's webinar...

- Is a reflection of my experiences and opinions
- Will give you some insight into the high-level practical aspects of doing bioinformatics
- Will provide you with some tips and tricks from someone who has learned the hard way
- Is intended to help you develop a basic understanding of the work involved in doing bioinformatics

Adjust your expectations

- Infinite compute
- Clear community standards
- Consistent data formatting
- Tools work out of the box
- Interoperable resourcing
- Accessible reference data

Expectation

Reality

- Limited compute and storage
- “That’s not how you use the HPC!”
- Many tools, same function
- Off by one errors
- Complex genome = complex compute
- “Just learn Python”

What is bioinformatics?

It is a scientific subdiscipline that involves the use of computing technology to collect, store, process, analyse, and disseminate molecular biological data and information.

It is an interdisciplinary field that develops and applies methods and software to understand biological data.

It combines the fields of biology, chemistry, computer science, computer programming, statistics, information engineering, and mathematics to do this.

Computational biology vs bioinformatics?

Y (@rob@genomic.social)
@nomad421

Should we draw a semantic distinction between the terms bioinformatics and computational biology? Are the differences substantial enough and the definitions well enough agreed upon ?

Yes; use them differently

51.6%

No; use interchangeably

48.4%

1,415 votes · Final results

9:55 am · 30 Jun 2022

Anyone who does distinguish between the terms does so differently.

I think:

- **Bioinformatics** tends to focus more on software and tool **development**.
- **Computational biology** focuses on the **application** of those tools.

But *what is it*, practically speaking?

The hidden aspects are essential to responsible and successful bioinformatics research:

- Big and complex data
- Data privacy and governance
- Code reproducibility
- Software management

A day in the life of a bioinformatician

A typical experiment

Study design

My groundbreaking genomics experiment

Research question:

- What genetic variations are associated with an increased risk of developing trait X in population Y?

Aims:

- Identify the genetic variants linked to increased risk of trait X.
- Evaluate the prevalence and functional impact of these variations in population Y.

Data:

- Whole genome sequencing data from population Y with and without trait X.
- Genome alignments, variants: SNPs and indels
- Reference assembly, genome annotations, known variants.

Methods:

- Collect and sequence gDNA from population Y
- Process raw data to identify SNPs and Indels
- Annotate variants for genomic location and function
- Perform statistical analyses to correlate variations with trait X

The same questions apply to every experiment:

- *What is the research question?*
- *What measurements will be made?*
- *What factors can influence measurements?*

What happens when you don't ask these questions?

- *Lack of focus on research question*
- *Inadequate or incorrect measurements*
- *Uncontrolled factors can invalidate results, leading to dodgy conclusions*

The data types

- The type(s) of data you choose for an experiment should reflect the biological question(s) being asked.
- Various sequencing types and sources. Each has its own benefits and drawbacks.
- Selective methods are focused on specific genes and regions. Ideal for targeted studies.
- High throughput methods are ideal for exploratory studies and novel discoveries.

Choose the right data

Relevance and specificity

Can it answer your research question?

Ethics

Do you need special approvals to work with this data? How will these impact data collection?

Resolution and granularity

What level of detail and insight is provided by this data?

Quality and accuracy

What error rates and types are associated with this data type?

Cost and resource efficiency

What sample size is required? How much will it cost to generate, process and store?

Where can I find data?

Service providers

Sequencing and mass spectrometry service providers can generate your raw data*.

Public datasets

Includes reference data, functional annotations, raw sequence, expression and array data.

Consortiums

Open source or controlled access to curated, aggregated, large-scale biological datasets.

The data formats

FASTQ	FAST5	FASTA	Sequence
CRAM	BAM	SAM	Alignment
gVCF	VCF	BCF	Variants
FASTA	GTF/GFF	BED	Reference
MZML	MZXML	RAW	Mass spectrometry
PED & MAP	PBD	BIGWIG	Specialised
+ many tool specific formats			

- Raw sequence, reference, and annotation data come in different formats for different purposes.
- Community standards on file formats to ensure consistency and interoperability across tools.
- Widely used formats have their standards published online.
- May look scary, but mostly just human-readable text files, compressed for efficient storage.
- Hands on exploration of your data is essential for understanding it.

The methods: pre-processing

The methods: analysis

- Lots of different methods to apply depending on the data type and research question.
- Ensure your chosen methods reflect the biological reality being studied.
- Methods should be statistically sound and appropriate for the data and research question.
- High complexity and large datasets can be computationally intensive, needing substantial disk space, RAM, and CPU power.
- Evaluate the methods you apply to ensure they meet community best practices and your specific needs.

The methods: interpretation

Where can I 'do' bioinformatics?

Where can I 'do' bioinformatics?

Graphical User Interface

Public and commercial platforms
Suitable for beginners/non-coders
Fixed methods and execution options
Integrated visualisations
Suited to small-scale processes

The image shows two screenshots of graphical user interfaces. The top one is the Galaxy Project interface, featuring a grid of blue circles and the text 'Galaxy PROJECT'. The bottom one is the Jupyter Studio interface, showing a code editor and a file browser. The text 'QIAGEN' is visible on the left side of the top screenshot, and 'jupyter' and 'Studio' are visible on the bottom screenshot.

Command Line Interface

Software installation and management required
Steep learning curve for beginners
Highly flexible and versatile
Not suitable for visualisation
Suited to processes of all size

The image shows a terminal window with a black background and white text. The prompt is 'georgie-cli:~\$'. The text is centered on the screen.

Practical tips

There is no “one size fits all” solution

Diversity in the data

Genome diversity, scale, population

Specificity of research questions

Each research question is unique and may require a different approach

So many methods!

Different tools and algorithms for the same task

End user preferences

Need for speed, low-no coding, customisation

Technologies are constantly evolving

Updating our approaches as we learn better ways

You're a life scientist, not a programmer*!

** Unless you actually are a programmer*

When you're starting out:

- Focus on understanding and reproducing your methods, rather than becoming a coding expert.
- View coding skills as a tool to achieve your research goals, not an end in themselves.
- Start with basic tasks and progressively develop your skills.
- Focus on understanding the logic of your code and getting it to work.
- Prioritise making your code functional and readable, rather than efficient.
- Take advantage of online treasure troves like GitHub.

Remember that your primary objective is to advance your research, not to master every coding language.

Don't reinvent the wheel

- The community is very collaborative and supportive.
- Engage with online communities and forums for advice, troubleshooting support, and experimental design.
- Get comfortable with different methods and data types through free training materials.
- Use open source software for data processing and analysis instead of writing your own from scratch.
- Use tools like containers, R packages, and Bioconda to manage software.
- Leverage public workflow communities like Galaxy, and nf-core to use and share standard workflows.

Learn how to ask questions

You receive an execution error.

You found a bug in a tool.

You have some general questions about a method.

You need project support.

Google it, talk to ChatGPT.

Contact the developer.

Join a community forum.

Talk to a bioinformatician.

Make contact

Error message(s), technical details to reproduce the error.

Technical details to reproduce (and resolve) the error.

Context, specific questions, concerns or considerations.

Context, what you've attempted, and where you are stuck.

What to provide

Don't trust your future self to remember anything

<https://www.markdownguide.org/>

```
## T2T mapping and variant calling

### Preprocessing
* Parabricks deepvariant_germline doesn't offer qc metrics output like fq2bam
* Running fq2bam, then deepvariant in 2 separate steps to collect alignment qc metrics
* To handle multiple fq pairs for a sample, used associative array in `make_input.sh` script
* Added validation and error checking for `make_input.sh` script, to avoid concerns regarding input streams

### Short variants
* Parabricks DeepVariant is currently supported for [V100s].
(https://docs.nvidia.com/clara/parabricks/4.0.1/documentation/tooldocs/man\_deepvariant.html#man-)
* Use of neural network means no need for known variants for annotation
* GLnexus not provided by Parabricks anymore, need to use CPU-based tool with Singularity
* Gadi queues do not have external network access, containers need to be downloaded before running `glnexus.pbs`

### Structural variants
* CHM13-T2T annotation db promised by AnnotSV, not yet. See [issue].
(https://github.com/lgmgeo/AnnotSV/issues/164)
* Run pipeline without AnnotSV for now
* Tried running with Tower as a test - successful
* Ran cohort GSV without annotsv with tower, ran in ~1.5 hrs
```

- Keep a code notebook that documents your process, issues, and justifications.
- Document **everything**, you'll definitely forget why and how you got to your results and conclusions.
- Comment your code so you and others know what it is doing.
- Version control your code to limit bugs and ensure its reproducibility.
- Implement tests to ensure your code is functioning as expected.
- Write and save utility scripts for basic, repetitive tasks.
- Save your code in repositories like GitHub or Bitbucket.

Takeaways

- Bioinformatic data is big, complex, and messy.
- Best way to learn is by doing, get stuck in.
- Your research context will dictate where and how you work.
- Collect the right data for your experiment!
- You will need to clean, process, analyse, and contextualise.
- Almost everything is open source.
- The community is very supportive, talk to each other!

Thanks!

Any questions?

You can email me at: georgina.samaha@sydney.edu.au